

Drive Test Across Europe for 5G Cellular Multi-Connectivity in Roaming Scenarios: The Livestock Transport Use Case

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Abstract—Although the deployment of 5G networks in urban environments is currently underway, rural areas suffer from cellular coverage limitations due to the poor deployment of 5G infrastructure. This fact directly affects use cases related to technology development in rural communities. As a result, key performance indicators may not meet minimums to satisfy a certain service, such as connectivity for livestock transport. As a strategy to improve the reliability of communications, the use of packet duplication through several cellular networks is proposed in order to increase robustness in areas with coverage issues. This study, which emulates livestock transport conditions through an experimental drive test across Denmark and Germany, demonstrates how packet duplication improves reliability for 4G/5G networks concerning latency Round-Trip Time and DL/UL throughput, on routes driven by livestock transport trucks.

Index Terms—5G, drive test, livestock transport, multi-connectivity.

I. INTRODUCTION

The livestock transport industry is continuously growing and requires connectivity solutions for the continuous transmission of sensor data for animal monitoring. This industry, which operates primarily in rural areas, relies on access to cellular technology connectivity solutions such as 5G. However, the current geographical deployment of 5G networks is mainly focused on densely populated urban areas. In contrast, the deployment of this technology in rural areas is limited due to low population density, which implies a lack of profitability due to high operating costs for telecom operators [1]. The implications of this fact are the emergence of a digital divide between urban and rural areas that increases inequality in access to communications technologies, affecting use cases that require connectivity solutions in rural areas [2]. The livestock transport companies envision a future where big amounts of data are shared constantly with the transport center and other regulatory bodies so that safety is increased, and a higher optimization of the trading process can be achieved. However, the sparse cellular coverage and poor connectivity performance in the main transport routes and in some rural areas where the farms or transport centers are located, does not always allow to meet the requirements, or enhance the digitalization of the livestock trading industry.

Within the framework of the COMNECT project [3], several use cases directly affected by this digital divide are addressed, developing solutions to improve the needs of rural communities through cost-effective and environmental-friendly connectivity approaches. In particular, this paper focuses on the monitoring livestock transport along rural routes. This use case addresses the issue of limited connectivity along Europe’s primary transport routes, which is crucial for optimizing routes and ensuring seamless reporting of location data and onboard sensor information to regulatory databases and fleet management centers [4]. Nowadays, the livestock transport industry is aiming for a connected ecosystem between trucks on the road, transport centers, and regulatory bodies, where a large amount of data about service status in the trucks is shared efficiently and with seamless connectivity. To this end, the application of multi-connectivity techniques is explored, since traditional single-connectivity solutions in rural areas may be unreliable in areas with poor or non-existent cellular coverage [5]. While most state-of-the-art research takes a theoretical approach [5]–[7], there is a gap in the validation of these solutions under real use case conditions. Thus, this work presents a drive test throughout Denmark and Germany that emulates a route driven by a livestock truck. The emulation of the connectivity conditions allows to exemplify the existing coverage issues in these areas, and how the application of cellular multi-connectivity between several mobile operators allows to partially mitigate this issue due to the simultaneous use of several cellular infrastructures. Specifically, this is done through the analysis of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) such as latency and throughput, under the assumptions of single-connectivity and multi-connectivity modes. Additionally, since these routes often cross several countries, it is assessed how the roaming condition affects the service of a cellular network between Denmark and Germany. Thus, the main objective of this study is to analyze the value of implementing multi-connectivity for cellular-cellular technologies given the above-mentioned future solutions of route optimization and remote support to livestock transporting units, on the move, and under the always changing physical conditions.

II. MEASUREMENT EQUIPMENT AND SCENARIO

This study is carried out through the joint implementation of two SIM8380G-M2 modems, operated through the Newport GW6400 computer. Each of these modems is capable of connecting to a commercial 4G/5G cellular network via a SIM card. For the tests, two SIM cards from two major Danish telecom providers have been used. Each modem connects to the cellular network through four omnidirectional antennas in the H-plane with 5 dBi gain. The GW6400 computer is equipped with *ping* and *iperf3* tools, enabling it to perform Round-Trip Time (RTT) tests using ICMP packets, and throughput (TP) tests via UDP traffic. Additionally, the execution of both tools is temporally aligned on both modems in order to evaluate in parallel the network performance in single-connectivity and multi-connectivity modes. Note that the modems are configured to attach exclusively to 4G and 5G networks, with 5G being the preferred network when available.

Based on the livestock transport use case, a route that emulates the one operated by the pig trading company DTL A/S (Padborg, Denmark) was used for navigation. For this purpose, DTL A/S provided us with a log file consisting of a travelled route between the city of Aalborg (Denmark) and five farms located in northwestern Germany. This route corresponds to a real use case where the truck is loaded in the north of Denmark and unloaded at the five farms mentioned above. The route, comprising a distance of approximately 750 km and 9 hours of driving (one way), is visualized in Fig. 1. Note that, on the outbound journey, network latency will be evaluated, while on the return journey, DL/UL TP will be assessed. Although the study focuses on a single route, it has been strategically designed to cover several conditions, providing a broader perspective on multi-connectivity solutions. According to the scenario and the available operators, this route can be divided into three main sections:

- **Denmark highway (Aalborg - Padborg, 290 km):** This section crosses the Jutland peninsula via a highway. Due to the traffic density, mobile operators serve this area through a high density of base stations. Since both SIM cards employed are from Danish operators, they will be connected to the operator home networks (Op. A and B).

Fig. 1. Journey between the cities of Aalborg and five farms in northwest Germany. The route comprises 1500 km (round trip) between Denmark and Germany. The five farms are marked in the inset (blue stars).

- **Germany highway (Padborg - Bremen, 280 km):** As in the previous section, good coverage conditions are expected due to the deployment of base station infrastructure along the highway. However, as the main difference, both SIM cards operate in roaming since they make use of the infrastructure of two German operators (Op. C and D).
- **Germany rural (Bremen - Cloppenburg, 180 km):** The third section includes the five farms where the truck unloads the livestock. It travels along local and regional roads in predominantly rural areas. This means the infrastructure available from the two German operators (Op. C and D) is lower due to the sparse population.

This route is carried out by mounting the measurement setup in a car. The GW6400 computer, the SIM8380G-M2 modems and the battery that provides power to both are located inside the vehicle, while the omnidirectional antennas are mounted on the vehicle's roof rack.

III. EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

A. Round-Trip Time Assessment

For the latency analysis, the RTT between the modems and a server hosted in Aalborg (Op. A and B in Denmark, and Op. C and D in Germany) is evaluated. This RTT is assessed every 100 ms synchronously between the two modems, thus being able to determine the performance in single-connectivity and multi-connectivity modes. Fig. 2 shows the empirical Probability Density Function (PDF) of the RTT values. While the equipment is connected to the local network in Denmark, an RTT predominantly between 20 ms and 25 ms is observed. However, when the modems are connected to the network via roaming networks (Op. C and D), a noticeable increase in the latency to values between 45 ms and 60 ms is observed. This increase is explained by the fact that the roaming data is routed through the local network in Denmark [8]. Note that for Op. C, the density of the distribution decreases notably in the rural area, implying that a high number of samples are shifted towards the tails. For Op. D, the distribution undergoes a shift of about 10 ms tending towards higher latencies. Despite this, these latency values satisfy the connectivity needs required in the livestock transport scenario [9]. However, these PDFs show a non-zero probability for $RTT > 100$ ms,

Fig. 2. Empirical probability density function of the RTT for the two SIM cards and four operators (Op. A and B in the home network, and Op. C and D in roaming) in the three scenarios considered.

Fig. 3. Empirical CCDF and CDFs of: (a) RTT, (b) DL and (c) UL throughput for the two SIM cards and four operators (Op. A and B in the home network, and Op. C and D in roaming) in the three scenarios considered given single-connectivity and multi-connectivity modes.

TABLE I
 $P(\text{RTT} < x)$ GIVEN SEVERAL SCENARIOS AND CONNECTIVITY MODES

RTT	Home Network			Roaming (Highway)			Roaming (Rural)		
	Op. A	Op. B	MC	Op. C	Op. D	MC	Op. C	Op. D	MC
100 ms	97.76	98.81	99.95	98.15	98.13	99.57	56.94	96.68	96.81
200 ms	99.42	99.43	99.997	99.42	99.45	99.87	66.00	98.88	98.94
300 ms	99.58	99.56	>99.999	99.63	99.67	99.91	69.97	99.25	99.28
400 ms	99.63	99.64	>99.999	99.69	99.80	99.94	72.12	99.41	99.43
500 ms	99.67	99.68	>99.999	99.73	99.88	99.96	73.75	99.53	99.54

hence the distribution tails have to be considered. Fig. 3(a) shows the empirical Complementary Cumulative Distribution Function (CCDF) of the RTT in the different scenarios emulating the livestock truck route. For $\text{RTT} < 100$ ms, the data distribution detailed in Fig. 2 is observed, where the latency for SIM cards operating in the home network is slightly lower than that of those networks operating in roaming. To assess the network reliability in the high latency regime, we proceed to analyze the distribution tails for $\text{RTT} > 100$ ms. In particular, a comparable distribution is observed in highways for Op. A and B in Denmark and Op. C and D in Germany, with network reliability for $\text{RTT} < 500$ ms between 99% and 99.9%. This fact suggests that roaming does not affect the distribution tails, i.e. high latency values, provided there are sufficient base station deployments as can be found on Danish and German highways. However, it is noteworthy that there is a slight worsening of latency in Op. D when moving from the highway scenario to the rural scenario. The same effect can be observed for Op. C, although much more noticeably with reliability below 75% for $\text{RTT} < 500$ ms. According to the infrastructure deployment map published by the German Federal Network Agency, the number of base stations in the rural area decreases for both telecom operators, and drastically in the case of Op. C, resulting in environments with limited coverage, which explains the low reliability. Note that the packet loss ratio can be inferred from $P(\text{RTT} > 500 \text{ ms})$, where coverage conditions imply the need for packet retransmission.

To further increase the network reliability, the CCDF is calculated in the case that both networks are enabled through multi-connectivity, i.e., duplicating packets to increase the robustness of communications. Therefore, the achieved latency is the one whose RTT between the two packets is lower since the routing through one of the network operators has

been performed more efficiently. These RTT distributions are also shown in Fig. 3(a). The curves show that although the multi-connectivity strategy does not improve the median RTT values, it does reduce the latency in the tails of the distribution. This is visible in the highway cases where reliabilities above 99.999% (home network) and 99.96% (roaming) are obtained for a maximum latency of 500 ms. In the rural case, since Op. C had poor connectivity, when packet duplication is performed, most packets are transmitted through Op. D, which causes the curve to be similar to the one observed for Op. D. Although in the latter case there is no clear improvement over the single-connectivity case of Op. D, it should be noted that the fact of applying multi-connectivity implies that the performance of the best of the available operators will be obtained as a lower bound, avoiding the large tails observed for Op. C. For comparison purposes, Table I shows the probability $P(\text{RTT} < x)$ for several latency thresholds.

B. Downlink and Uplink Throughput Assessment

For downlink and uplink TP analysis, the *iperf3* tool is used, which requests 14/1 Mbps in DL/UL according to the requirements defined in COMECT for the livestock transport use case. In summary, requirements for proposing route optimization services with Quality of Experience (QoE) include continuous availability of content such as updated satellite maps, road conditions, livestock risk zones, or weather forecasts, with tolerated loading times of 3 to 5 seconds [9].

Fig. 3(b) shows the empirical CDF for the DL TP in each scenario. Both scenarios on the highway are able to ensure DL values close to 14 Mbps with reliability higher than 90%, from where the TP starts to decrease until reaching null connectivity for reliabilities between 99% and 99.9%. Note that all the operators, both in the home network and in roaming, show similar trends, with median DL values close to 14 Mbps and similar distribution on the tails. In the case of connectivity in the rural area, Op. D performance worsens when moving from the highway to the rural area, as it was observed in the latency analysis. As for Op. C, it shows the worst performance with null TP at around 19% of the time analyzed, in line with the high latency values found for this operator in the rural area. For the multi-connectivity case, also shown in Fig. 3(b),

there is a remarkable decrease in the CDF tails due to the simultaneous availability of both networks. In particular, this is noticeable in the scenarios on the highway in Denmark and Germany where at least 12 Mbps can be served 99.13% and 98.59% of the time, respectively. Similarly, non-zero TP is observed 99.99% and 100% of the time, respectively. In the rural scenario, the distribution resembles that shown for Op. D, due to its superior performance over Op. C.

Regarding the uplink evaluation, Fig. 3(c) presents the empirical UL TP CDFs for the different scenarios. Compared to the DL, the UL is more constrained by suffering from null TP values with reliabilities between 90% and 99% for highway scenarios. This reliability decreases below 90% for the rural case, even decreasing to 73% for Op. C, indicating that 27% of the time the modem is not able to establish a connection. When the multi-connectivity strategy is applied, coverage on the highway, both in the home network and roaming, improves substantially, avoiding null coverage with reliability between 99% and 99.9%, and providing values close to 1 Mbps with reliability above 95%. In the rural case, the application of multi-connectivity allows obtaining non-zero coverage with reliabilities above 90%, compared to values below 90% in single-connectivity.

C. Discussion and guidelines

The previous results have shown a generalized improvement of all the proposed KPIs when applying multi-connectivity based communications in the three proposed scenarios along the driven route, and in particular, in the rural scenario. In more detail, it has been found that the median RTT values increase significantly when the connection to the network is switched from the home network to roaming, which has been tested with two modems and four different mobile operators. It is also worth noting the similarity in CCDF tails given the highway scenarios independent of the roaming condition. Comparing scenarios, rural areas suffer a strong latency degradation due to the lack of infrastructure versus the route driven on highways. This fact is especially remarkable for one of the operators, whose $P(\text{RTT} < 100 \text{ ms})$ goes from 98% on highways to 57% on rural roads. In this case, the use of multi-connectivity does not ensure performance improvements, although it does establish a lower performance bound equal to that of the best of the available operators. In terms of TP, both DL and UL are not affected by the roaming condition, with similar distributions in both cases under the assumption of a scenario with similar characteristics. As expected from the latency results, the rural scenario achieves lower TP values compared to its highway counterpart. It is also found that the UL is more constrained than the DL, even when 1 Mbps is requested in UL versus 14 Mbps in DL. In both cases, the application of multi-connectivity improves the TP targeted reliability.

For the deployment of an interconnected ecosystem between regulatory agencies, transport centers and trucks, these results envision the possible use of advanced applications for real-time route optimization, real-time monitoring with video or predictive analytics. For instance, the bandwidths

and latencies achieved with multi-connectivity strategies could enable continuous exchange of live data on traffic, weather, and road conditions, AI-driven route planning algorithms and cloud processing, live video streaming to control centers or predictive models for truck and livestock conditions using sensor data.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This work has presented a drive test that emulates the connectivity conditions in the rural use case of livestock transport. Along the route between Denmark and Germany, latency and throughput (DL and UL) in single and multi-connectivity cases have been assessed on highways and in rural areas, taking into account connections to home networks and in roaming. The results show that the simultaneous use of two cellular networks match or substantially improve the performance of the network in single-connectivity mode. Future work will include analyzing packet duplication strategies to reduce the additional cost introduced by the multi-connectivity approach.

In summary, the benefit of multi-connectivity integration for the livestock transport use case is demonstrated, and it can be considered as a solution given the coverage issues faced by the communications systems available on these routes. These benefits not only facilitate seamless reporting of location data and onboard sensor information to regulatory databases and fleet management centers but also enable route optimization and planning applications based on big data analysis in real-time.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe program COMMECT (Under Grant Agreement No: 101060881).

REFERENCES

- [1] L. Chiaraviglio *et al.*, "Bringing 5G into Rural and Low-Income Areas: Is It Feasible?," *IEEE Communications Standards Magazine*, vol. 1, no. 3, pp. 50-57, 2017.
- [2] A. Lappalainen and C. Rosenberg, "Can 5G Fixed Broadband Bridge the Rural Digital Divide?," *IEEE Communications Standards Magazine*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 79-84, 2022.
- [3] Horizon Europe, "COMMECT: Bridging the digital divide and addressing the need of Rural Communities with Cost-effective and Environmental-Friendly Connectivity Solution," [Online]. Available: <https://www.horizoneurope-commect.eu/>.
- [4] COMMECT, "D1.1: Report on end-users' needs and relevant use cases," Deliverable 1.1, Horizon Europe, 2023.
- [5] M. G. Kibria, K. Nguyen, G. P. Villardi, W. -S. Liao, K. Ishizu and F. Kojima, "A Stochastic Geometry Analysis of Multiconnectivity in Heterogeneous Wireless Networks," *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, vol. 67, no. 10, pp. 9734-9746, 2018.
- [6] M. Simsek, T. Höbller, E. Jorswieck, H. Klessig and G. Fettweis, "Multiconnectivity in Multicellular, Multiuser Systems: A Matching-Based Approach," *Proceedings of the IEEE*, vol. 107, no. 2, pp. 394-413, 2019.
- [7] L. Jiao, J. Zhao, Y. Xu, T. Zhang, H. Zhou and D. Zhao, "Performance Analysis for Downlink Transmission in Multiconnectivity Cellular V2X Networks," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 11, no. 7, pp. 11812-11824, 2024.
- [8] R. A. K. Fezeu *et al.*, "Roaming across the European Union in the 5G Era: Performance, Challenges, and Opportunities," *IEEE INFOCOM 2024 - IEEE Conference on Computer Communications*, Vancouver, BC, Canada, pp. 2378-2387, 2024.
- [9] COMMECT, "D1.2: Report on COMMECT requirements and KPIs," Deliverable 1.2, Horizon Europe, 2024.